

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
EV	Electric Vehicle
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DoA	Description of Action (Annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DSO	Distribution System Operator
FO	Flexibility Operator
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OCMP	Open capacity Management Protocol
OCP	Open charge Point Protocol
PLC	Power Line Communications / Carrier
PUC	Pilot Use Case
PV	Photo voltaic
SOC	State of Charge
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the final methodology used by each of the pilots. This final methodology is based on the references to KPIs included in deliverable D.10.2 and in the individual pilots' obligations stated in the DoA.

Each pilot bases their final methodology on this first period experiences, with specific adjustments, to fulfil these obligations. This description includes the final steps to be taken in the implementation process, to be prepared for the final tests, to achieve the expected results.

This deliverable defines and describes all the processes for each pilot according to the implementation process and the deviations according to the individual DoA obligations.

Apart from the General KPI's, common for all pilots, each pilot will strive to prove their individual KPIs. This final methodology needs to be prepared and support these individual goals.

1 Introduction

This document shows the final methodology and steps that the pilots have followed from the beginning of the project until now.

In the previous deliverables a timeframe was defined to be followed in order to establish a guideline for the installation and integration for all pilot tasks.

Likewise, a series of key performance indicators (KPIs), both general and specific for each pilot, were defined.

This document is a revision and update of the deliverable D10.2, with explanatory supplementary information to meet their individual DoA obligations.

Figure 1. Basic process showing the different main steps. The arrows mark the transitions whereby performance tests will be performed according to KPIs specified.

Figure 1 shows the main steps in the process to meet the objectives of each pilot and answer the research questions that were specified in the deliverable D10.1.

Final Pilot methodology deliverable describes test and validation processes and the test criteria that will meet the KPI requirements set forth, the promises in the DoA per pilot and highlight the promised impacts in the DoA. This means that test cases must be designed that will prove the pilot case with respect to the DoA and the pilot's own KPIs.

Figure 2. INVADE process

In the following section all the processes and KPIs implementation processes will be described for each one of the pilots.

2 PUC description

As it was described and defined in other deliverables, all the Pilot Use Cases (PUC) are:

- PUC-1: Mobile energy storage using EVs for V2G, V2B and V2H operations
- PUC-2: Centralised energy storage using an array of batteries at the sub-station or street level
- PUC-3: Distributed energy storage using individual batteries at the household level
- PUC-4: Hybrid level energy storage solutions addressing a combination of use cases 2 and 3

PUC overview for all pilots

This table gives an overview of which PUCs to be valid in the different pilot`s.

Table 1. Use Cases related to Pilots

Pilot	PUC-1	PUC-2	PUC-3	PUC-4
Norway - Lyse	X		X	
The Netherlands – Greenflux/Elaad	X			
Bulgaria - Albena	X	X		
Spain - EPESA		X		
Germany - badenova				X

3 Key Performance indicators

The different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are listed in the tables below. They are organized according to each use case defined and will be explored within the different pilots. All KPIs are listed as general to apply for all pilots. Then, the overview for each specific pilot with dedicated KPIs is listed, and commented with “local customization”. All KPIs are related to the research questions listed in deliverable D10.1.

3.1 General KPIs

General KPIs common for all pilots have been listed in Table 2 and explained below.

Table 2. General KPIs

KPI no	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	Standard defined methodology used to reduce time of adaptation in Scaling up the pilots. This KPI should prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”.	To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It’s important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database.	All
2	KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households. KPI= actual response / theoretical response with no latency	To demonstrate the improvement of using batteries due to better % usage, and at the same time reduce the probability of black-outs. Lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to reduce power-peaks.	All

3	<p>KPI for sizing of the battery in new, efficient households VS old households, to improve efficiency and reduce power-peaks / costs.</p> <p>This KPI reflects the size in kWh vs. peaks. (lengths & heights)</p> <p>KPI = peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]</p>	<p>This recommendation will reflect the sizing of the battery due to different kinds of connected basic loads, and fast-acting loads with limited duration.</p> <p>This will prove how households with “modern heating” and “0” base-loads will have very quick ROI when power-tariffs will be introduced.</p> <p>Battery cost = energy capacity * unit cost</p>	1, 3
4	<p>Same as the KPI above, but also including the possibility to curtail basic loads, and move usage in time.</p> <p>KPI = base reduction / battery cost [kWh/€] = unit battery cost</p>	<p>This recommendation will prove the necessity of curtailing basic loads in combination with batteries in “old” households to achieve the efficiency, and to meet new tariff-structure.</p>	1, 3
5	<p>KPI will prove the % improvement in charging with a dynamic smart charging “system” vs. charging systems not reflecting the “valley-filling” possibilities within the smart charging. KPI 30% improvement.</p> <p>Volume of valley without smart charging = V1</p> <p>Volume of valley with smart charging = V2</p>	<p>To compare the models of charging with a fixed setting of the maximum capacity reflecting the limitation in the installation in worst case vs. the Smart Charging model. Smart Charging using dynamic set points and predictions due to input from big data analytics.</p>	1, 3

	KPI $\geq 1 - V_2/V_1 = 0,3$		
6	Same KPI as above, but now introducing DC-charging with OCPP 2.0, with reverse energy-flow.	Proving the new possibilities within the OCPP 2.0, giving the possibilities to balance the grid when including the reverse energy-flow. Again, reduce the risk of exploit the Grid / “living on the edge” without increasing the risk of black-outs, and to avoid “comfort-curtailing” when EV is connected.	1 (Elaad, Lyse)
7	KPI will prove the quality-improvement of including the battery in the installation. Reflecting the standards of quality measuring like: Example: TDH = Total Harmonic Distortion < 5%	This KPI will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling of including the battery in an installation. Both on households / building level and on the substation level.	All

4 Tests inputs - General KPIs

4.1 Test: prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”

4.1.1 Purpose

To prove the benefits of using open standard protocols and reducing the possibilities of brand specific customizations. It's important to avoid local “tailor-made” solutions that will influence on the scalability, both in time and in re-structuring of register/database. Applies to all use-cases.

4.1.2 Abstract

Standard defined methodology used to reduce time of adaptation in scaling up the pilots. This KPI should prove that “timeframe” for adapting new customers is “0”.

4.1.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

Installation ready for test, and supporting the test steps.

4.1.4 Test steps

Table 3. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Add new recipient of flexibility	Flexibility customer established within xx seconds	
2.	Define contract between FO and flex recipient	Contract established within xx minutes	
3.	Check communication through open standards and protocols between recipient and FO according to contract defined	Recipient is able to execute and communicate instructions according to	

		contracts (latency < xx seconds)	
4.	Add new flexibility provider	Flexibility provider established within xx seconds	
5.	Define contract between FO and flex provider	Contract established within xx minutes	
6.	Check communication based open standards and protocols between flex provider and FO according to contract defined	FO is able to execute and communicate instructions according to contract (latency < xx seconds)	
7.	Repeat steps 1-3 for 5 different, randomly picked recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	
8.	Repeat steps 4-6 for 50 randomly picked and different recipients	System performance remains stable with no degradation of response	

4.2 Test: demonstrate the improvements using batteries

4.2.1 Purpose

This is a comparative test. To demonstrate the improvement of using batteries due to better % usage, and at the same time reduce the probability of black-outs. Lower safety margin and maximum utilization in the installation to reduce power-peaks.

4.2.2 Abstract

KPIs proving the reduction of the vulnerability in latency by using batteries in households.

$KPI = \text{actual response} / \text{theoretical response with no latency}$

This implies that the response time for compensation of loss of power is measured and compared to a pilot requirement or theoretical standard.

4.2.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Theoretical response” has been defined.

Amp meter connected to the battery.

4.2.4 Test steps

Table 4. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Send activation signal from FO. Start clock at point of activation.	Activation executed. Clock started.	
2	Monitor the amp meter connected to the battery. Record time to amp meter change- Record the response time and meter reading at activation.	Response time reading Amp meter reading	
3.	Compare with theoretical measure	Ratio	
4.	Rerun test in the following manner: Simulating a black out.	Run new tests after adjustments	

5.	Disconnect power. Simulate black out		
6.	Repeat steps 1-3		

4.3 Test: peak reduction vs cost – modern houses

4.3.1 Purpose

This will prove how households with “modern heating” and “0” base-loads will have very quick ROI when power-tariffs will be introduced. Based on a KPI for sizing of the battery in new, efficient household’s vs old households, to improve efficiency and reduce power-peaks / costs.

4.3.2 Abstract

This recommendation will reflect the sizing of the battery due to different kinds of connected basic loads, and fast-acting loads with limited duration.

Battery cost = energy capacity * unit cost

This KPI reflects the size in kWh vs peaks (lengths & heights).

KPI = peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]

4.3.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

“Normal” or default consumption is defined for test objects.

SOC status is 100% (80%) before all activations.

Test in new households (passive houses)

Meter readings are known prior to activation.

Concrete KPI must be defined prior to the test.

4.3.4 Test steps

Table 5. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Engage battery for 30 minutes. Measure the drop-in power consumption. Measure SOC after 30 minutes	Difference in SOC Drop in meter reading	
2.	Disconnect battery, measure the raise in power readings. Calculate average flexibility yield for battery across 30 minutes.	Raise in meter reading	
3.	Compare SOC change to battery specifications. Calculate peak reduction and relative peak reduction.	Peak reduction Peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]	
4.	Repeat steps 1 – 3 for 1 hour, 1,5 hours, 2 hours and 2,5 hours		

4.4 Test: peak reduction vs cost – older houses

4.4.1 Purpose

This recommendation will prove the necessity of curtailing basic loads in combination with batteries in “old” households to achieve the efficiency, and to meet new tariff-structure.

4.4.2 Abstract

Same test as the one above. Same as the KPI above, but also including the possibility to curtail basic loads, and move usage in time.

KPI = base reduction / battery cost [kWh/€] = unit battery cost

4.4.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

KPI is defined prior to test.

4.4.4 Test steps

Table 6. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
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1.	Engage battery for 30 minutes. Measure the drop in power consumption. Measure SOC after 30 minutes.	Difference in SOC Drop in meter reading	
2.	Disconnect battery, measure the raise in power readings. Calculate average flexibility yield for battery across 30 minutes.	Increase in meter reading	
3.	Compare SOC change to battery specifications. Calculate peak reduction and relative peak reduction. Must comply with predefined standard.	Peak reduction Peak reduction / battery cost [kW/€]	
4.	Repeat steps 1 – 3 for 1 hour, 1,5 hours, 2 hours and 2,5 hours.		

4.5 Test: Valley filling: Smart Charging vs charging with fixed settings

4.5.1 Purpose

To compare the models of charging with a fixed setting of the maximum capacity reflecting the limitation in the installation in worst case vs the Smart Charging model. Smart Charging using dynamic set points and predictions due to input from big data analytics.

4.5.2 Abstract

KPI will prove the % improvement in charging with a dynamic smart charging “system” VS charging systems not reflecting the “valley-filling” possibilities within the smart charging.

KPI \geq 30% improvement.

Volume of valley without smart charging = V1

Volume of valley with smart charging = V2

KPI \geq $1 - V2/V1 \geq$ 0,3

4.5.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

A set of minimum 5 charging points (11 or 22 kW) for the test has been defined

A set of minimum 5 identical EVs has been made available for the test

All EVs have identical SOC level under 40%

4.5.4 Test steps

Table 7. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Charge EVs without the external control. Monitor the raise in SOC (SOC profile amp & V) Monitor the accumulated load	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
2	Repeat step 1 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
3	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity and a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours)	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
4	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity and a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours)	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
5	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours) and the INVADE optimizer	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
6	Compare results and compare	$KPI \geq 1 - V2/V1 \geq 0,3$	

4.6 Test: V2G – DC/Chademo

4.6.1 Purpose

Proving the new possibilities within the OCPP 2.0 and 15118 (ed. 2), giving the possibilities to balance the grid when including the reverse energy-flow.

4.6.2 Abstract

Same KPI as above, but now introducing DC-charging with OCPP 2.0, with reverse energy-flow. Again, reduce the risk of exploit the Grid / “living on the edge” without increasing the risk of black-outs, and to avoid “comfort-curtailing” when EV is connected.

4.6.3 Assumptions and Pre-Conditions

- We need EV's in the pilot that are capable of reverse energy-flow charging
 - Elaad acquired a Nissan Leaf for this purpose
- The drivers/owners of the EV's might need extra warranties for usage of their battery for V2G
 - We will be using our own car, which mitigates this pre-condition
- We need a fully functional charging station for V2G, which has proven to be difficult to find
 - As a fall-back scenario a stationary battery has been purchased. The battery can be operated instead of the Nissan Leaf.

OCPP 2.0 was not released in time and thus not available for V2G usage and testing. Nevertheless, V2G will be tested in the Dutch pilot at Elaad premises using OCPP 1.6. This will also show the possibilities and possible gaps in the OCPP protocol to support V2G supply.

4.6.4 Test steps: new asset, area and zone

Table 8. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1	Charge EVs without the external control using the V2G charger.	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV	

	Monitor the raise in SOC (SOC profile amp & V) Monitor the accumulated load Compare results to regular chargers	Aggregated load profile	
2	Repeat step 1 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
3	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using fixed setting of the maximum capacity and a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours)	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
4	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions, using a standardised day-routine of charging-discharging-charging	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
5	Repeat step 2 with identical preconditions using a time frame of regular parking (2, 4, 8 hours) and the INVADE optimizer, taking into account both charging and discharging as possible performance of charger.	SOC profiles per EV Load profiles per EV Aggregated load profile	
6	Compare results of all steps	KPI $\geq 1 - V_2/V_1 \geq 0,3$	

4.7 Test: measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling by including a battery

4.7.1 Purpose

This KPI will measure the improvement in voltage stability / noise (odd harmonics) cancelling of including a battery as part of an installation. This should be done at both for at household level, building level and on substation level.

4.7.2 Abstract

KPI will prove the quality-improvement of including the battery in the installation. Reflecting the standards of quality measuring like:

Limiting max. voltage level on grid connection point to a given level given by law or standard.

4.7.3 Assumptions and pre-conditions

In many countries maximum and minimum voltage levels are given by law or standard. For example in Germany appliances in household must operate within a voltage range of 230V+/- 10%. But on the grid connection point of distributed energy sources the max. voltage increase is actually limited to a much lower value of +3%.

4.7.4 Test steps

Table 9. Test steps

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Identify day expecting significant voltage increases due to high PV-generation and low load (e.g. sunny Sunday afternoon).		
2.	Track activation of automatic local voltage control using online monitoring.		
3.	Local voltage control is activated, if on one of the three phases a preset trigger level is exceeded.	Algorithm started	
4.	Track, if local voltage control is able to reach the preselected target value, which is lower than 230V+3%.	Voltage decreases and reach target value	
5.	Track, how much energy flow from the battery is needed to keep the preselected target value over the time.	kWh	

5 Specifics for the pilot in Norway

5.1 Objectives

5.1.1 Goals

The Lyse pilot investigates and demonstrates the intersection between V2H/loads/PV, effect-based tariffs and energy management in private homes and buildings, and how they are combined in new business models.

From a business point of view, we believe that these kinds of services at a household level will create both customer value as downstream services in the retail market and future upstream services on a DSO level.

5.1.2 Main results

Through the pilot it is desired to show the effect and benefit of smart management of energy-efficient components in the home in order to better utilize their own energy consumption. It is expected that the pilot will provide the necessary answers to how energy efficient a home can be by using new technology and the INVADE platform.

The desired achievements are related to optimal consumption of self-produced solar power and power management throughout the day to get the lowest possible power bill for the end customer. The commercial side of the pilot will be to look at how one can make money selling flexible services to end customers and how this should be handled. The result of the pilot will also be decisive for the choice of business model.

5.1.3 Final list of KPIs to be measured

Table 10. KPIs specifically for the Norwegian pilot

KPI	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	Optimize energy consumption based on hourly rate.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, to adapt to different tariffs. (time of use)	1

2	Optimize energy consumption based on effect/power	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, to adapt to different tariffs. (peak-power)	1
3	Optimize utilization of self-produced energy.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, for self-consumption vs feed-in to the grid.	1

5.1.4 Implementation process

For the different types of “sub-pilots”/locations in the pilot, there will be a different time frame for the implementation process.

According to the deliverable D10.2 and the time frame defined, all the tasks and subtasks state is explained and detailed below:

Contracts and legal entities:

December 2017 – February 2018

Clarify legal relationships between customer and supplier related to contractual requirements and obligations.

Clarify the legal relationships between customers and suppliers was done to ensure the right development of contracts for the pilots in the project according to GDPR. Protection of customer data and customer ownership to data had to be solved as a part of the technical solution. The use of customer data and how this would be treated in the project was described in the pilot contract with each pilot owner.

Sales and recruitment of pilots /sign contracts:

January 2018 – March 2019 (Households), April 2018 – May 2018 (Housing cooperatives)

Campaign management, customer contact, customer meetings and customer agreements

The pilots have been recruited through social media and existing sales channels. The benefit by doing this is the existing delivery process for equipment which enables effective deployment of pilots.

Two Housing associations has been recruited, but with a longer process because they only take decisions on investments in the General assembly held twice a year.

Installation:

January 2018 – March 2019 (Households), April 2018 – May 2018 (Housing cooperatives)

Coordinate device vendors and field engineers to minimize customer impact. Install customer equipment

The equipment that was already supported through existing sale channels was successfully delivered as a part of the daily routine for Lyse Energisalg AS and Smartly AS. The rest of the equipment that was not supported in the existing sale channels was installed at the same time. Not all equipment was installed. We are still missing the HAN-reader to be installed. This is still pending in the pilot.

Piloting and collecting data:

June 2018 – end of the project

Poll relevant data sources on agreed intervals and deliver relevant data on defined format to eSmart

To prove that the INVADE platform can be inter-operable with existing smart solutions or ecosystems, we integrated the local ecosystem/Smartly platform with the INVADE platform. This was done through standardized protocols and APIs. The resolution and which format and data to share between the platforms was agreed with eSmart.

Integration Fronius PV:

January 2018 – June 2018

Develop and integrate a polling API towards Fronius and re-format the data to event based forwarding DataStream to eSmart

Testing and validation of implementation

Communication with Fronius to get necessary documentation on the API provide to integrate their PV cloud solution. Development of the Smartly platform to integrate the protocol and API. Successful test showed that the protocol and API's worked as expected.

Cloud to cloud integration is the most beneficial way of integration if scalability and stability is important.

Integration Eaton Battery:

January 2018 – June 2018

Develop and integrate a polling API towards Eaton and reformat the data to event based forwarding data-stream to eSmart

Testing and validation of implementation

Communication with Eaton to get necessary documentation on the API provide to integrate their battery cloud solution. Development of the Smartly platform to integrate the protocol and API. Successful test showed that the protocol and API's worked as expected.

Integration to HA-platform:

January 2018 – June 2018

Implement event-based integration to HA-platform

Testing and validation of implementation.

Development of the existing HA- platform to support the event-based communication towards the INVADE platform was necessary to develop with respect to the standardized event-based API between the platforms. Successful test showed that the protocol and API's worked as expected.

Integration Weather Data:

January 2018 – March 2018

Prepare Smartly weather data source for INVADE GUI

Testing and validation of implementation

Successful test showed that the protocol and API's worked as expected.

App development:

April 2018 – October 2018

Implement INVADE GUI functions in the Smartly customer app

Testing and validation of implementation, release of new functionality, step by step.

The Smartly customer app was further developed with new functionality to support the INVADE services and customer engagement. 3 versions were made to be tested and validated. This was done successfully

B2B integration INVADE – Smartly:

January 2018 – December 2018

Clarify requirements of data entities, define API-standard, develop, implement and test agreed API

Testing and validation of implementation

This work has been done as a cloud to cloud integration between the two platforms. The project has developed and implemented a standardized API for easy onboarding of new customers which enables easy setup of pilots. This also enables easy upscaling of new customers after the project. Dataflow from the Smartly ecosystem to the INVADE platform was implemented as an event-based solution. Any new event at the customer site will generate data to the INVADE platform. The INVADE platform provides AI based on the input/data from the existing ecosystem and adds value by creating a control plan for optimization to our pilot. Testing between the platforms has been done successfully.

5.2 Pilot Norway KPIs tests

Following the structure of Section 4, include the test for the KPIs in each pilot. With the purpose, assumptions, pre-conditions, and steps of all the KPIs

Table 11. KPIs specifically for the Norwegian pilot

KPI	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	Optimize energy consumption based on hourly rate.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, to adapt to different tariffs. (time of use)	1
2	Optimize energy consumption based on effect/power.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, to adapt to different tariffs. (peak-power)	1

3	Optimize utilization of self-produced energy.	To test different set-ups of battery / flexible loads, for self-consumption vs feed-in to the grid.	1
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5.2.1 Norway

5.2.1.1 Test 1: Optimize energy consumption based on hourly rate

5.2.1.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of switching off low priority components when the energy price is high to save money.

5.2.1.1.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

To measure the KPI we need data from the power meter over a period of time (normal consumption) to create data to compare with the optimization algorithm. Before and after INVADE optimization, functionality is implemented.

5.2.1.1.3 Test steps

Table 12. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect data from main power meter before implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Collect data from main power meter after implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Compare between data from before and after implementation of algorithms	Get Reliable comparison between data before and after implementation of algorithms.	

5.2.1.2 Test 2: Optimize energy consumption based on effect/power

5.2.1.2.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of even out consumption during the day by turning off low priority components when the consumption is high.

5.2.1.2.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

To measure the KPI we need data from the power meter over a period of time (normal consumption) to create data to compare with the optimization algorithm. Before and after INVADE optimization, functionality is implemented.

Table 13. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect data from main power meter before implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Collect data from main power meter after implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Compare between data from before and after implementation of algorithms	Get Reliable comparison between data before and after implementation of algorithms.	

5.2.1.3 Test 3: Optimize utilization of self-produced energy

5.2.1.3.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of optimal consumption of self-produced solar power and power management throughout the day to get the lowest possible power bill.

5.2.1.3.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

To measure this KPI we need data from the power meter over a period of time (normal consumption) to create data to compare with the optimization algorithm. Before and after INVADE optimization, functionality is implemented.

Table 14. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect data from main power meter before implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Collect data from main power meter after implementation of algorithms.	Get reliable data	
Compare between data from before and after implementation of algorithms	Get Reliable comparison between data before and after implementation of algorithms.	

5.3 Pilot Norway deviations

What are the main deviations detected in the project regarding the planned in D10.2 and what are the corrective actions proposed to solve these deviations?

1. The pilot has grown in number of users and scale compared to the DoA. The background for this is input from the PO regarding scale. We added payment for pilots to participate in the project to get more pilots and more engagement into the project. This means that the number of pilots at this stage is higher than the number of pilots described in the DoA. It will not affect the budget but need to be communicated to the PO as a deviation.
2. We have a delay in the pilot role out. This is caused by the Norwegian standardisation on HAN connection and power meter data collection which is important for the pilot to function.

We will come with a plan for how to solve this.

3. There has been a delay with the availability of the INVADE platform. There is a plan developed for onboarding our pilot.

6 Specifics for the pilot in The Netherlands

6.1 Objectives

6.1.1 Goals

The pilot in The Netherlands will be focused on the impact of electric vehicle charging on the electricity network and the possibility to use as much as possible renewable energy, meanwhile keeping the energy grid in balance. This will be done as much as possible with the use of standard or de-facto standard protocols between systems.

There are two ways of looking at flexibility. From a commercial situation which GreenFlux will do in the pilot and from DSO perspective to protect the grid which will be done by Eelaad.

The goal of the whole project is to manage the external influences on the grid and prevent that the grid will fail because of these changing inputs and outputs. Our pilots show that EVs can play a major role in this as they are one of the most demanding energy sources, but also one of the most flexible ones for energy management.

Largest challenge is to combine multi-stakeholder optimization (both energy prices and grid constraints).

6.1.2 Main results

For supporting INVADE and the communication of charge profiles to and from the INVADE cloud, the OCMP protocol is developed. This enables us to actively manage flexibility in the grid by smart charging based on consumption and expected production data.

Objectives from DSO (Eelaad) point of view:

- Protecting the grid and quality of service with the behaviour of charging is managed by taking the max kW on the grid and based on that use more or less charging and more or less usage of stationary batteries as balancing mechanisms.
- From Commercial side this flexibility should not affect the business and households when done on large scale. The DSO pilot with over 700 public chargers show that when each charger is using limited flexibility this can have large positive effects on the grid. By combining the chargers in virtual groups, like in districts, this effect is simulated and proven.

Objectives from the charge point operator (GreenFlux) point of view:

Related to semi-public chargers at parking / large scale parking pilot:

- Optimizing KW-max (load balancing/peak shaving) and energy prices (opportunistic charging) saves money
- Maximizing the use of local renewable energy production for EV charging reduces redelivery
- For these services GFX can ask a fee from the consumer

Related to HOME pilot:

- No price incentives for the customer, except for charging during off-peak hours (23u – 7u)
- Commercial model between GFX and grid operators

6.1.3 Final List of KPIs to be Measured

Table 15. KPIs specifically for the Dutch pilot

KPI no	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	The share of renewable energy	To show the improvement in share of renewable energy	1
2	The kW-max for the grid connection	To demonstrate the optimization of the available grid-capacity vs EV-charging control	1
3	APX price effects	To demonstrate the APX price-effects	1
4	Session duration	To demonstrate effects in session duration	1

6.1.4 Implementation process

For the different types of “sub-pilots”/locations in the pilot, there will be a different time frame for the implementation process.

According to the deliverable D10.2 and the time frame defined all the tasks and subtasks state is explained and detailed below:

1) February 2018

Establish and confirm protocols, data exchange agreements with third parties (especially eSmart) coherent with pilot design.

The OCMP protocol was defined in February 2018 and was specified and tested until May 2018. Also, the data exchange agreements were finalized.

Result: OCPM protocol v1.0 specifications. Agreement with eSmart (INVADE cloud) what and how the data is exchanged between the INVADE cloud and the systems from Elaad and GreenFlux.

2) February - March 2018

Develop user recruitment plan

a) Describe the necessary hardware facilities

Elaad defined the specifications for the stationary battery and several charge stations to be used for the INVADE pilots. Also, first attempts have been made to acquire the V2G chargers, which were not yet available. GreenFlux acquired hardware for the controllers to be used with the INVADE pilots for Smart Charging, dealing with the charge profiles.

b) Develop pilot user agreements

Pilot user agreements within existing legal framework have been setup taking into account future V2G possibilities. Existing user agreements were updated.

c) Develop communication materials: webpages, newsletters, press releases

Press releases have been sent out for the Elaad test facilities, which are part of the INVADE pilot and GreenFlux sent out press release about the achievements for INVADE so far. In several newsletters from GreenFlux and Elaad INVADE was mentioned as important step towards future energy grid balance.

3) February – June 2018

Active user recruitment

a) Facility / hardware checks**b) Platform onboarding**

All pilot sites were successfully connected to the cloud. Real time data imported GreenFlux and Elaad databases. Elaad and GreenFlux prepared the hardware and software modification on their own system to be ready for the INVADE platform integrations.

4) **May – June 2018**

Platform and API integration tests

Elaad and Greenflux did the first platform and integration test with the developed OCMP protocol with eSmart. Successful test showed that the protocol and API's worked as expected.

5) **July 2018 – June 2019**

Deployment / roll-out

- a) July Initial roll-out (approximately 10-20% of the pilot users, 20-50% of local hardware)
- b) September - October Full roll-out (first to all customers, then to all charge points on the customer's sites).
- c) December Flexibility adjustments based on preliminary results

From August 2018, we started with the roll out and activation of the Dutch pilot assets (chargers, battery). Until the connection with INVADE eSmart Cloud system was life first week of December, we started with the base measurements to be able to compare the data before and after the connection with the eSmart INVADE Cloud.

In total over 700 public charge points are connected, 350 semi private charge points at business and company parking's and 25 private charge points at homes. Also, a test system with energy storage and a V2G charger is part of the pilot and connected to the eSmart INVADE cloud.

Between March 2019 and June 2019, the optimization algorithms should become part of the INVADE cloud which will enable the NL pilot to improve the profiles and energy flexibility.

During January 2019, first pilot results were put in D10.4.

6.2 Dutch pilot KPIs tests

Following the structure of Section 4, include the test for the KPIs in each pilot. With the purpose, assumptions, pre-conditions, and steps off all the KPIs.

6.2.1 The Netherlands

6.2.1.1 Test 1: Share of renewable energy

6.2.1.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the amount of renewable energy that is used in EV-charging (or total energy consumption).

6.2.1.1.2 Assumptions and Pre-conditions

Baseline measurements are performed in order to establish the zero situation. In this state, no smart charging is performed. These measurements include energy consumption and EV-charging data.

For this test, forecast data is used to forecast the renewable energy production on the location. Real time consumption and EV-charging data is also considered by the smart charging algorithm in order to establish the optimal charging capacity.

It is assumed that the forecast data is representative for the corresponding production location. Also, it is assumed that the smart charging algorithm can adjust the optimal capacity in such a way that it is beneficial for the level of renewable energy consumption.

6.2.1.1.3 Test steps

Table 16. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect baseline measurement data on renewable energy usage	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	
Renewable energy production forecast data is sent to the INVADE platform		
This data is used to optimize the EV-charging capacity		
Collect smart charging data on renewable energy usage	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	

Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	
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6.2.1.2 Test 2: KW-max for grid connection

6.2.1.2.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the kW-max of the grid connection. This is the maximum amount of energy that is consumed from the grid connection, measured in power output (kW).

6.2.1.2.2 Assumptions and Pre-conditions

6.2.1.2.3 Test steps

Table 17. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect baseline measurement data on total energy consumption	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	
Collect smart charging data on total energy consumption	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	
Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	

6.2.1.3 Test 3: APX price effects

6.2.1.3.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the average price per kWh for EV-charging during the session.

6.2.1.3.2 Assumptions and Pre-conditions

In order to show the effects of the consumption profile on the average price per kWh, it is assumed that all monitored grid connections have access to flexible pricing schemes. Also, because of the small scale of the pilot, it is assumed that the pilot has no influence on the APX-price.

6.2.1.3.3 Test steps

Table 18. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect baseline measurement data on total energy consumption and corresponding prices	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	
Collect smart charging data on total energy consumption and corresponding prices	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	
Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	

6.2.1.4 Test 4: Session duration

6.2.1.4.1 Purpose

The purpose of this KPI is to show the impact of the smart charging algorithm on the duration of the session.

6.2.1.4.2 Assumptions and Pre-conditions

The session duration is here defined as the period between the start of charging until a full EV-battery.

6.2.1.4.3 Test steps

Table 19. Test steps

	Expected result	Result
Collect baseline measurement data on session duration	Reliable baseline data for comparison with smart charging data	
Collect smart charging data on session duration	Reliable smart charging data for comparison with baseline measurement data	
Compare baseline measurement data with smart charging data	Reliable comparison between baseline and smart charging data for a sufficient period of time	

6.3 Pilot Netherland deviations

The biggest deviations are related to the delay in optimization of the profiles via the INVADE cloud as the optimization algorithms are later available than expected. Also, the INVADE platform itself was later available than expected. Both were solved by:

- Starting the pilots with base line measurements
- Using historical data to start already profile optimization.

7 Specifics for the pilot in Spain

7.1 Objectives

7.1.1 Goals

The objective of the Invade project is to make a better use of existing energy storage technologies by creating value to the end users, through a cloud-based platform. This platform aggregates and manages the storage equipment and makes its energy available for the final users, which can be prosumers, EV owners, DSO's or BRP's.

Aligned with the overall objective of the project, the aim of the Spanish pilot is to test and validate the use of the Invade platform to manage one centralized energy storage system in bringing value to the final users (DSO and BRP) in its daily operations. The main goals

are to test the use of the battery in providing flexibility services to the DSO and validate its ability to manage grid congestions, control voltage levels and support its control centre room in island mode, contributing to the developments of its abilities on facing the current and future challenges on the electrical grid. The goals of the Spanish pilot also include the validation of the use of flexibility from the energy storage to provide self-balancing optimization services to the BRP which will aim to use this flexibility to lower the imbalance costs of its portfolio.

7.1.2 Main results

In D10.2, the following expected outcomes for the Spanish pilot validation were defined:

- Control and observability of the LV network
- Facilitate at the DSO as a part of the open market for services
- Participation of distributed generation and energy storage in network Management
- Provide back-up service to head quarter
- Optimised market interactions of the BRP (cost savings for the BRP)

Regarding the first point, observability of the LV network is already in place in the Spanish pilot, due to the installation of grid measurement devices on the substations of the pilot location. This observability is important because it is with this data that the DSO can make predictive analysis of congestion problems over its grid and act with flexibility (from the battery) in time to avoid it; gaining therefore control over the grid. Control over the LV network is also expected through the power electronics device, installed together with the battery at the substation site.

The second expected outcome, respect to the facilitation of the DSO as part of the open market for services, is a result that would be applicable if the Spanish laws would allow DSOs to have energy storage systems as assets to participate in flexibility services. At the moment this is not allowed in the Spanish law, and therefore this result is not applicable. Nevertheless, the findings can facilitate this integration in case of regulatory changes.

The third and fourth expected outcomes are both related with the flexibility services tested with the DSO scenario. Once the communication with the Invade platform is implemented, these two services can be validated. The same is applied to the point five, which can be validated once the operations with the Invade platform are running.

7.1.3 Final list of KPIs to be measured

With the objective of evaluating the success of the implementation of the Invade concept on the Spanish pilot, a set of KPIs was defined in D10.2 and is listed in table below.

Table 20. KPIs specifically for the Spanish pilot

KPI no	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	Congestion reduction issues	% of reduction in congestion problems	2
2	Energy and power reduction	% of reduction in voltage/reactive power problems	2
3	Islanding time	Amount of time-controlled islanding can be sustained	2
4	BRP cost savings	% of BRP cost savings in the FO scenario compared to the scenario with no FO	2
5	Capacity of the grid	% of increase in hosting capacity in the grid	2
6	Grid investments reduction	% of decrease in future grid investments necessary in the FO scenario compared to the scenario with no FO	2
7	Optimization Diesel Generation	% of decrease in emissions from the diesel generator previously used to offer controlled islanding to the DSO control centre	2

7.1.4 Implementation process

For the different types of “sub-pilots”/locations in the pilot, there will be a different time frame for the implementation process.

According to the deliverable D10.2 and the time frame defined all the tasks and subtasks state is explained and detailed below:

- 1) Global architecture design – during this phase, the main achievement was the confirmation of the architecture to be implemented in the Spanish pilot, being defined that the main flexibility source comes from the centralized battery installed at the substation of the company’s headquarters, and the flexibility users

would be the DSO and the BRP, confirming then the applicability of UC2 in this pilot.

- 2) Internal design – this phase was postponed to a later period of the project, due to the construction work that started at the company’s headquarters, affecting the electrical infrastructure of the pilot area. The construction work finished around M18 and the process could be validated by then.
- 3) Construction phase – this phase started around June 2018, where the grid measurement devices were being installed at the pilot location and was finalized with no major delays. This phase included also the installation of the battery and power electronics device at the substation, which was completed at the beginning of 2019 and is currently under testing and validation activities. Field data exchange and integration with the SCADA systems is currently being carried out according with the defined dates on D10.2; these activities are expected to be finished by June 2019.
- 4) Test and commissioning – this phase is expected to occur from March to November 2019 and include the testing activities such as validating the SCADA database, integration of field data, check BMS and power electronics technology. Activities respect to the integration and testing of the Invade platform are also expected during this period.
- 5) Final Outcomes – activities related with results and outcomes are expected to occur during the final two months of the project – November and December 2019.

7.2 Spanish pilot KPIs tests

Following the structure of Section 4, this section includes the test for the KPIs in the pilot, with the purpose, assumptions, pre-conditions, and steps off all the KPIs

7.2.1 Test 1: Congestion reduction issues

7.2.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this scenario is to evaluate the amount of congestions avoided in the pilot location over a certain period by means of activating flexibility through the flexibility operator. The scenario follows a methodology which starts by collecting nearly real-time data from the pilot location and is composed by 5 main steps:

1. Data collection from the secondary substations of the pilot location – in this step, data regarding active and reactive power consumed is being collected from the substations in periods of 15 minutes.
2. Forecasts – this step consists on making forecasts of the active and reactive power values on the substations included in the pilot area.
3. Power Flow Simulations – the third step consists on running power flow simulations with the forecasted values obtained from the previous step. In this stage, the results from the power flow simulator identify possible congestions in the grid.
4. Optimal Flexibility Power Flow Simulations – with this simulation the system is able to identify the amount of energy needed from the battery in order to avoid the congestions which were predicted in the previous step.
5. Invade – the final step consists in the interaction with the Invade platform, where the flexibility requests are sent requesting the energy needed by the DSO.

7.2.1.2 Assumptions and preconditions

The pilot is constituted by one battery of 212 kWh of capacity and a power electronics device with 100 kW of maximum power output. This equipment is installed at a secondary substation on the area of EPESA's headquarters. As part of the pilot area there is also one primary substation and nine more secondary substations.

The methodology described above will be applied with the pilot data and there are three locations where congestion management will be tested out:

- Case 1 - At the feeder of the primary substation
- Case 2 –The distribution transformer (MV/LV) of the secondary substation node, where the equipment is installed
- Case 3 – Cable that connects the MV side of the transformer of the secondary substation node to the primary substation E.R. REC

Figure 3. Conceptual scheme of the congestion management scenarios

During the implementation of the project, the headquarters of EPESA went through construction work which changed part of the EPESA infrastructure and updated the grid topology that affects the pilot. These changes made that the affectation of a battery with the capacity of 212 kWh had little implication considering the new characteristics of the grid on the pilot area. For this reason, the current scenario tested in the actual conditions is less likely to encounter grid congestions; nevertheless, for conceptual testing purposes, during the tests, theoretical values of the grid cables and transformer will be considered in order to validate the concept under a testing environment. These assumptions will be described in the final document presenting the results.

To quantify the KPI % of reduction in congestion problems, the following equation is used:

$$(\%) \text{ Congestions}_{Reduction} = \frac{\text{Cong}_{NoFO} - \text{Cong}_{FO}}{\text{Cong}_{NoFO}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Where Cong_{NoFO} corresponds to the number of congestions related with overpassing current maximum operational limits, identified on the pilot location over the testing period, in a scenario without the flexibility operator.

Cong_{FO} represents the number of congestions avoided on the pilot location over the same testing period, in a scenario with the flexibility operator. This KPI measures the % of congestions avoided in the grid of the pilot location by the flexibility operator.

7.2.1.3 Test steps

This test includes running the simulations described in section 7.2.1.1 with real data from the pilot area in order to validate the concept of avoiding grid congestions by means of activating flexibility through the flexibility operator. The simulations will run for a certain period and conclusions will be taken out of the obtained results. Therefore, the test is composed by two main steps, described in the table below.

Table 21. Test steps for KPI – Congestion Reduction Issues

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Run the simulations (described in section 7.2.1.1) over a certain period.	Number of congestions identified in the pilot area over the test period	
2.	From the congestions identified in step 21, identify the ones which were solved by the FO through the INVADE platform.	Number of congestions avoided, thanks to the FO	
3.	Using equation 1, calculate the KPI – Congestion reduction issues	KPI is quantified	

7.2.2 Test 2: Energy and power reduction

7.2.2.1 Purpose

The electrical distribution losses accounts for most of the power losses in the entire system. For that technical losses occur when the energy is dissipated by the equipment

and conductors in the distribution lines. The losses depend on the network characteristics, and mode of operation. There are two categories of technical power losses; the fixed technical losses and the variable technical losses.

The fixed losses in the distribution lines account for between a quarter and a third of the total technical losses. These are usually in the form of heat and noise and occur whenever the transformer is energized. The fixed losses are not influenced by the amount of load current flowing, but rather by the leakage current losses, open circuit losses, and dielectric losses.

The variable losses are proportional to the square of the load current and accounts to between 2/3 and 3/4 of the technical losses in a distribution system. The variable losses arise due to the line impedance, contact resistance and the joule heating losses.

The largest amounts of these losses occur in the primary and secondary distribution lines and can be classified as either technical losses or non-technical losses.

7.2.2.2 Assumptions and preconditions

The storage modelling exercise will be carried out using an operationally focussed current impact in terms of four reactive quadrants and the active power concerning the SoC and DoD model to determine the real capacity located in SS modelling for the rest of SS involved in the pilot following constraints and market price signals.

7.2.2.3 Test Steps

Table 22. Test steps for KPI - Energy and Power Reduction

1.	Check SoC battery	80%	
2.	Generate a signal to charge the battery	Increase up to 90%	
3.	Generate a signal to discharge the battery	Decrease up to 70%	

4.	Obtain the module value and signal of the current	+/- A	
5.	Check the contribution in LV bus bar in SS.	A,V	
6.	Check the contribution in MV feeder in PS	A,V	
7.	Model and simulate for the other 10 SS.	-	

7.2.3 Test 3: Islanding time

7.2.3.1 Purpose

Islanding occurs when a distributed generator keeps feeding a certain part of the network, that is disconnected from the main grid. It is a commonly used strategy within critical buildings, for which the connection with electricity is imperative for its important functions.

In the Spanish pilot this scenario is tested. The control centre room of the DSO (figure 4) is considered a critical building, since, from here, the distribution grid of EPESA is monitored and controlled 24/7. At present, this room is backed up by a diesel generator, which ensures the power supply in case of an eventual electric failure.

In this scenario, the use of the energy from the battery is tested as a backup electricity source of the control centre room, avoiding thus the usage of the diesel generator and the consequent CO₂ emissions.

The purpose of this test is to validate the controlled islanding scenario, through a set of defined tests that simulate the case of an electrical failure that affects the control centre room of the DSO and verifies the capability of the system to back up the critical building with electricity from the battery for a period of two hours.

Figure 4. Critical building – Control centre room of EPESA

7.2.3.2 Assumptions and preconditions

During this test, an electrical failure is simulated in order to assess the possibility of the electrical backup of the critical building being done with the supply of energy from the battery instead of the diesel generator.

During the pilot tests, 50% of the battery capacity (about 100 kWh) is reserved to give back-up service to the critical building, whereas the other 50% is used by the FO to provide flexibility services to the DSO and the BRP.

7.2.3.3 Test steps

Table 23. Test steps for KPI - Islanding Time

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Check available capacity battery	100kWh are reserved and available for this test	
2.	Check consumption critical building doesn't exceed the maximum PED power	- test emergency settings	
3.	Ensure that critical loads are connected under UPS systems		

4.	Check the PED is synchronized to loads		
5.	Switch to mode island PED and send command to open LV SW gear to grid		
6.	Monitoring parameters among expected values according: U, P, Q, Hz		
7.	Monitoring SoC Battery		
8.	After 15 minutes, synchronize PED to Grid		
9.	Switch in mode slave PED	-	
10.	Monitoring suitable functionalities	-	

7.2.4 Test 4: BRP cost savings

7.2.4.1 Purpose

A BRP is a market participant who is responsible for the imbalances in the electric system. Imbalances occur every time electricity generation doesn't match electricity consumption, within a given period. In the Spanish pilot, this scenario will be tested by Mercator, the electric retailer which is part of EPESA's company group.

Self-balancing portfolio optimization aims to lower the imbalance costs of the BRP's portfolio, activating flexibility. By continuously forecasting its portfolio electricity demand, the BRP might be able to predict future deviations and activate flexibility in order to avoid them. Overall the BRP's main objective is that the cost of this activated flexibility is lower than the cost it would have on imbalance settlement over the same period.

The purpose of this test is to evaluate the cost savings that the BRP has when activating flexibility over a certain period, with the goal of avoiding deviation costs.

7.2.4.2 Assumptions and preconditions

At the moment, the BRP buys the electricity to cover its portfolio demand in the day-ahead market. To address the current scenario, the BRP will update the predictions of

its portfolio consumption during the current day and request flexibility whenever there is an unbalance predicted. To run this scenario, the BRP makes also daily predictions of the direction of the electric systems' unbalance in order to support its decision before making the flexibility requests to the Invade platform. These steps are schematized with a flow process in Figure 5.

This test is applied over the pilot location and therefore, the portfolio of clients of the BRP is assumed to be the set of clients that corresponds to the geographical location of the pilot.

Figure 5. Process of BRP's scenario

The % of cost savings in this scenario is quantified according with the following equation:

$$(\%) \text{ BRP cost savings} = \frac{CBRP_{NoFO} - CBRP_{FO}}{CBRP_{NoFO}} \cdot 100 \tag{2}$$

$CBRP_{FO}$ → costs of the BRP in the scenario with the flexibility operator (€)

$CBRP_{NoFO}$ → costs of the BRP in a scenario without the flexibility operator (€)

% BRP cost savings → % of BRP cost savings in the scenario with the FO compared with the scenario without the FO

Where the mentioned variables are quantified according with the following assumptions; all costs are related to the testing period in which the test will run:

$$CBRP_{FO} = C_{electricityDA} + C_{FlexibilityRequests} + C_{imbalance} + C_{contracts} + C_{soft1} \quad (3)$$

$$CBRP_{NoFO} = C_{electricityDA} + C_{imbalance} \quad (4)$$

$C_{electricityDA}$ → Costs of electricity purchases in the day ahead market (€)

$C_{FlexibilityRequests}$ → Costs of purchasing flexibility from the FO (€)

$C_{imbalance}$ → Costs on deviations (€)

$C_{contracts}$ → Costs associated with the contracts between the BRP and the FO (€)

C_{soft1} → Costs associated with software improvements needed to permit the interaction of the BRP with the FO (€)

Costs related with human resources, infrastructure and other variables indirectly related with the costs of a BRP are neglected during this analysis, since they are not considered to change significantly when comparing both scenarios. These variables are assumed to have little variation in the scenario with or without the FO and therefore having low impact on the result, therefore are neglected.

7.2.4.3 Test steps

Once the systems are running, this test consists in measuring the costs on flexibility requests done by the BRP and comparing them with potential deviation costs that the BRP would have in a scenario without flexibility, within the same period.

Table 24. Test steps for KPI - BRP cost savings

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Run the simulations described in section 7.2.4.1 for a certain period in order to	Costs associated with flexibility requests are quantified	

	quantify the cost that the BRP has in flexibility requests.		
2.	Quantify the variables associated with the costs of the BRP in the scenario with and without the FO, using equations 3 and 4.	BRP costs with and without FO are quantified	
3.	Quantify the % of BRP cost savings with equation 2.	% of BRP cost savings in a scenario with FO compared with no FO is quantified	

7.2.5 Test 5: Capacity of the grid

7.2.5.1 Purpose

Capacity is likely the newest term to everyone; it is a measure of the potential for power delivery. The capacity is metered as monetary units (euros) per time unit of an hour, per MW of power that flows. The price of energy is just Euros per MWh, which end up as the same effective unit cost metric.

In traditional distribution cables and power systems, we have distribution and power transformers with a size is set by the maximum power. The capacity of a cable and transformer in terms of the potential to distribute a flow of power in MW, the same units as power.

The capacity factor is the fraction (from 0-1; or a percentage from 0-100%) of flow utilization over the duration of a load. This fraction as a ratio of the power cable and transformer true output (evaluated over a period) relative to the potential power output that would occur ideally when operating full out for an indefinite period.

7.2.5.2 Assumptions and preconditions

In order to analyse impacts of energy, different modelling approaches can be derived. However, the results of even the best energy system model will highly depend on the underlying input data.

First, in this contribution the importance and availability issues of grid data in the distribution grid.

Second, we will focus on power grid modelling based of the 10 SS using the DCU available data.

The proposed methods provide transparent assumptions, simplifications and documentation of grid modelling. This results in the ability to validate, discuss or reproduce the results of energy pilot.

In the Spanish pilot there is no renewable generation and therefore the increase in hosting capacity on the grid is provided and can be measured using the PED. With injection and ejection of P(kW) and Q(kVAr) at the substation level, the increase in the hosting capacity of the grid can be measured in three different points, represented conceptually on Figure 5. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**

This KPI is therefore measured using the following equations, applied to the three different points of the pilot location.

$$(\%) \text{ Increase}_{\text{Hosting Capacity Grid 1}} = \frac{C1_{\text{Actual}} + C1_{\text{withFO}}}{C1_{\text{Actual}}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

Where,

$(\%) \text{ Increase}_{\text{Hosting Capacity Grid 1}} \rightarrow$ % increase in hosting capacity on point 1 of the grid

Figure 5 $C1_{\text{Actual}} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 1 in a scenario without the flexibility operator (A)

$C1_{\text{withFO}} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 1 in the scenario with the flexibility operator (A)

$$(\%) \text{ Increase}_{\text{Hosting Capacity Grid 2}} = \frac{C2_{\text{Actual}} + C2_{\text{withFO}}}{C2_{\text{Actual}}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

Where,

$(\%) \text{ Increase}_{\text{Hosting Capacity Grid 2}} \rightarrow$ % increase in hosting capacity on point 2 of the grid

(Figure 5

$C2_{\text{Actual}} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 2 in a scenario without the flexibility operator (A)

$C2_{\text{withFO}} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 2 in the scenario with the FO (A)

$$(\%) \text{ Increase}_{\text{Hosting Capacity Grid 3}} = \frac{C3_{\text{Actual}} + C3_{\text{withFO}}}{C3_{\text{Actual}}} \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

Where,

(%) $Increase_{Hosting\ Capacity\ Grid\ 3} \rightarrow$ % increase in hosting capacity on point 3 of the grid (Figure 6)

$C3_{Actual} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 3 in a scenario without the flexibility operator (kVA)

$C3_{withFO} \rightarrow$ maximum operational limit at the measurement point 3 in the scenario with the FO (kVA)

7.2.5.3 Test steps

Table 25. Test steps for KPI – Capacity of the grid

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Measurements – this action composes the measurements of grid values at a certain instant (measurements of I [A], transformer capacity [kVA]) in points 1, 2, 3 and 4 represented in Figure 5 At this point, values $C1_{Actual}$, $C2_{Actual}$ and $C3_{Actual}$ are quantified.	Values of I [A] and transformer capacity [kVA]	
2.	PED interaction – this action includes the operation of the PED with injection/ejection of P [kW], Q [kVAr]	PED injects/ejects P [kW] and/or Q [kVAr]	
3.	Measurements – this action implies the measurement of grid values at the same measurement points as step 38 in order to quantify the incremental changes. In this step values $C1_{withFO}$, $C2_{withFO}$ and $C3_{withFO}$ are quantified.	Values of I [A] and transformer capacity [kVA]	
4.	Quantification - this step corresponds to the comparison of results and quantification of the % increase in hosting capacity for the current scenario, by applying equations 5, 6 and 7.	% increase in hosting capacity in the grid	

5.	Simulation – this step corresponds to the application of the results on a simulated scenario in order to quantify the current KPI over the other 10 SS.	-	
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The following picture represents the topology of the secondary substation node, where the battery and PED are installed. In yellow circles are identified the points in which the increase in hosting capacity will be quantified with the current test.

Figure 6. Conceptual scheme of the points of measurements at the SS node

7.2.6 Test 6: Grid investments reduction

7.2.6.1 Purpose

The need for investment in capital intensive electricity networks is on the rise in many countries. A major advantage of distributed resources is their potential for deferring investments in distribution network capacity. This pilot outlines how an economically efficient portfolio of distributed generation, storage, demand response and energy

efficiency can be integrated as network resources to reduce the need for grid capacity and defer demand driven network investments.

Locational pricing can reduce the investment needs arising in distribution networks from the transformation towards smart grids with high shares of renewable generation.

Locational signals in a general tariff plan for either energy or network pricing require substantial system reform which impedes feasibility. The pilot proposes smart contracts with locational elements as hybrid form. System reform is only modest since contractual solutions emerge in smart grids anyhow. But, the responsibility for tariff setting stays with the network operator. The regulator's task is limited to incentivizing efficient network investment and allowing network operators maximum flexibility in contract design

7.2.6.2 Assumptions and preconditions

The methodology, key assumptions, and results of a quantitative evaluation of the investment needed (costs) for an envisioned Smart Grid, and it represents a partial segment of the DSO grid. It also offers a preliminary estimate of benefits of implementing a Smart Grid. This test is a framework for discussing possible levels of investment to achieve a fully functioning Smart Grid. It is not a definitive analysis of all attributes or costs of enhancing the power delivery system. The cost estimate was built upon a number of key assumptions:

Incorporate technologies that not only make the electricity delivery system smarter, but also stronger, more resilient, adaptive.

Include every reasonable and cost-effective enhancement to accommodate regulatory mandates.

Incorporate technology and policies that enhance pilot functionality while meeting load growth, expanding and modernizing the power delivery system

Assume simultaneous deployment of Pilot functionality. While deployments will realistically be made along parallel paths and in traditional or discrete steps, this test assumes they will occur simultaneously and continuously.

Total power delivery investment costs will exceed Pilot investments. They will include investments to meet load growth and to maintain reliability.

Appropriately operating and maintenance (O&M) costs associated with running utilities which this pilot technologies. O&M expenses are a substantial part of total costs and are built into rates at estimated levels. The IT and technology O&M aspects of the Smart Grid need to be included in cost estimates.

This KPI will be calculated according with the following equation:

$$(\%) Decrease_{GridInvestments} = \frac{InvestmentGrid_{NoFO} - InvestmentGrid_{FO}}{InvestmentGrid_{NoFO}} \cdot 100 \tag{8}$$

(%) $Decrease_{GridInvestments}$ represents the % of decrease in future grid investments necessary in the FO scenario compared to the scenario with no FO.

$$(\text{€}) InvestmentGrid_{NoFO} = C_1 + C_2 + C_3 \tag{9}$$

Where C_1, C_2 and C_3 correspond to the cost of replacing the material at point 1, 2 or 3 anytime there is one or more congestions measured at that point in the scenario without the FO. C_1 is the cost of replacing the feeder at the primary substation (point 1 in Figure 6), C_2 is the cost of replacing the transformer of the secondary substation Node (point 2 in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) and C_3 is the cost of replacing the underground cable that connects the primary substation to the secondary substation Node (point 3 in Figure 6).

$$(\text{€}) InvestmentGrid_{FO} = C_4 + C_5 + C_6 + C_{sw2} + C_{hw} \tag{10}$$

Following the same assumptions of the previous equation, C_4, C_5 and C_6 correspond to the cost of replacing the material at point 1, 2 or 3 anytime there is one or more congestions measured at that point in the scenario with the FO.

C_{sw2} → added costs that the DSO has in automating the software systems that allow the congestions management through the Invade platform.

C_{hw} → hardware costs that allow the congestion management.

During the test the following assumptions are considered:

Assumption 1 – in both scenarios it is assumed that whenever exists one or more congestion at any of the three measured points, the corresponding material (cable or transformer) would need to be replaced to avoid the congestion.

Assumption 2 - C_1, C_2 and C_3 are assumed to be zero in the case where no congestions are identified at the corresponding point.

Assumption 3 – it is assumed that the costs C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5 and C_6 include the cost of the material which will be replaced, as well as operation and installation costs.

7.2.6.3 Test steps

Table 26. Test steps for KPI – Grid Investments Reduction

	Action	Expected result	Result
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1.	Run simulations described in section 7.2.1.1 over a certain period.	Number of congestions in points 1, 2 and 3 are identified	
2.	Quantify the costs of avoiding the congestions in a scenario without the FO.	Costs of avoiding congestions without the FO are identified	
3.	Apply equation 8 to quantify this KPI.	% decrease in future grid investments in scenario with FO are identified	

7.2.7 Test 7: Optimization Diesel Generation

7.2.7.1 Purpose

The purpose of this test is to quantify the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided by not having to use the diesel generator as a backup system for the control centre room.

As mentioned previously, during the controlled islanding scenario, the battery will be used to supply the critical building with electricity for two hours. The main goal of this test is to understand the advantages of using a battery as backup service instead of the diesel generator, which is associated to expensive fuel costs and CO₂ emissions.

Therefore, this KPI's intention is to measure the % of decrease of CO₂ emissions from the diesel generator when supplying the critical building with electricity in islanding mode from the battery system.

7.2.7.2 Assumptions and preconditions

Estabanell Energia (Mercator) is an electricity retailer which commercializes only electricity from renewable sources. For the test purposes, it is assumed that the flexibility operator buys the electricity needed to charge the battery from Mercator and therefore the CO₂ emissions associated with the battery usage are negligible.

This KPI was defined in D10.2 as “% of decrease in emissions from the diesel generator previously used to offer controlled islanding to the DSO control centre”, however, after making the previous assumption, where the use of the battery does not imply on CO₂ emissions, it is decided that instead of measuring this KPI as a % it will be measured in quantify (in g) of CO₂ emissions avoided in the current scenario. With this measurement

it will be possible to better quantify the impact on CO₂ emissions reduction when using the battery as a backup support for the critical building. The method is described in the next section.

7.2.7.3 Test steps

This test consists in calculating the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided when using the battery system to supply the control centre room with electricity over the testing period, comparing with its previous supply with the diesel generator.

$$DecreaseCO_2 = t_1 \cdot CO_2(dieselgenerator) + t_2 \cdot CO_2(dieselgenerator) \quad (11)$$

DecreaseCO₂ → amount of CO₂ emissions avoided in the current scenario (g)

t₁ → time in which the critical building is supplied by the battery system in island mode (h)

t₂ → time in which the diesel generator is up and running only for testing purposes (h)

CO₂(dieselgenerator) → CO₂ emissions of the diesel generator (g/h)

Table 27. Test steps for KPI – optimization diesel generation

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Run test 3 in order to validate the controlled islanding scenario	<i>t₁</i> is quantified	
2.	Apply equation 11 and quantify amount of CO ₂ emissions from the diesel generator	KPI is quantified	

7.3 Spanish Pilot Deviations

The planning of the implementation of the Spanish pilot was presented in D10.2 and figures in the image below.

No major delays are identified in regards with the planning. The activities related with the integration of the Invade platform is an activity part of the Test phase, which started in January 2019 and is planned to continue until the end of the Test phase (5/11).

Figure 7. Planning of the Spanish pilot implementation (presented in D10.2)

8 Specifics for the pilot in Germany

8.1 Objectives

8.1.1 Goals

The Central Energy Storage (CES) provides a solution for the DSO to control and improve the power quality of the grid in a selected area with a weak end-feeder and a high penetration of PV-generation. Another main goal will be achieved by successfully incorporating two separate value streams within one single battery. In addition to the autonomously working voltage control algorithm another business case is to be actively executed by the INVADE platform on request of the grid control centre to avoid peak load fees to the entire electrical grid of bnNETZE. So, the DSO can benefit twice which makes the investment in the battery more profitable.

Beside this eleven “energy pioneers” willing to actively shape the future of the energy industry were found for the project. The PV storages of these energy pioneers are to be controlled by the central INVADE platform as a superior management authority at certain times. The already installed home management systems take the role of a local energy management authority at the unit level and are overruled by INVADE from time to time. This sub pilot offers auxiliary services to the DSO as well. In addition to the prosumer self-balancing that already takes place, the PV-batteries are also used for peak shaving. A request from the DSO triggers the process to calculate an optimized schedule for the battery usage. After running the optimization, a control signal is sent back to the households to regulate the residual load at the grid connection point of each household. In return, the customer receives lower grid usage tariffs for acting grid-friendly, as he provides the DSO the access for flexible control of the household.

8.1.2 Main results

The sub-pilot with CES exemplarily demonstrates the possibilities of large-scale batteries to offer services to the DSO in general and to improve the power quality locally at the same time. It is expected that the battery is autonomously able to handle the situation with occasionally occurring voltage quality issues at the weak end-feeder.

Therefore, last year during a very hot and sunny period high-resolution power quality measurements have been conducted in the relevant grid area. Based on the voltage values of all three phases simulations have been elaborated to analyse the influence of

dedicated battery charging and discharging on the voltage level. On this basis trigger values have been extrapolated and the local voltage control algorithm has been designed. This algorithm is transferred already in software code and comes into effect, when the redox flow battery is fully operational.

In addition, measurement data of the entire electrical grid of bnNETZE has been analysed to locate the days with economically relevant power peaks over the year. It could be proven, that only for ten to twenty days in the year, it must be expected, that a relevant peak load will occur. This means, that under normal circumstances the local voltage control algorithm can work without external disruption. Only on a view day over the year an overruling by the higher management level is likely.

8.1.3 Final list of KPIs to be measured

Table 28. KPIs specifically for the badenova pilot

KPI no	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	DSO cost savings	Cost savings of the DSO compared to other solutions such as grid enforcement or other types of control devices	2
2	Additional DSO cost Savings	Cost savings regarding the peak power fees to the upstream network operator	1 and 2
3	Additional revenues for private households	Amount of additional revenues for customers compared with common approach of optimizing self-sufficiency only	1
4	Frequency of flexibility Usage	How frequently is flexibility requested by the DSO provided by DES and CES	1 and 2
5	Flexibility potential of DES	Testing and examining the flexibility potential that DES can offer in addition to the actual purpose of optimizing self-consumption	1

8.1.4 Implementation process

For the different types of “sub-pilots”/locations in the pilot, there will be a different time frame for the implementation process.

According to the deliverable D10.2 and the time frame defined all the tasks and subtasks state is explained and detailed below:

Central Energy Storage (CES)

Following steps are done:

- Screening of possible test sites within the bnNETZE grid
- Evaluation of all possible test sites and decision for one based on an assessment in several dimensions
- Decision making process between Lithium-Ion and Redox-Flow
- Specification for the redox-flow-battery
- Procurement process
- Contract with the manufacturer
- Production of the battery
- Delivery of the battery on site and connection to the grid
- Development of a local voltage control algorithm
- Preparation of interconnection with the grid control centre

Pending:

- Communication tests with grid control centre
- Communication test with INVADE platform (depending on progress in other WPs)

Distributed Energy Storages (DES)

Following steps are done:

- New contract type for interconnecting customer premises elaborated
- 11 customers (“energy pioneers”) have been contracted
- Communication hardware is installed
- Internal communication tests are completed
- Operational data is visible on the SMA platform

- Control tests are completed

Pending:

- Communication test between SMS portal and INVADE platform (depending on progress in other WPs)

It should be noted that other WPs are still working on the flexibility request concept, which will be utilized in the German pilot, and this has to be implemented in the INVADE platform when the concept is done. This will need some time. Based on these remarks following time frame results:

Table 29. First draft for Implementation process

Phase	Description	Start-up	End	Phase dependencies	Comment
Platform integration and API test	API integration performed and an API test conducted.	Already started	28/02/19		A test of the communication should be performed when the integration is finished. This should be done according to the D7.4 INVADE document. It is suggested that this test is done week 10 (starting with the 4 th of March) due to heavy work load with several INVADE deliverables during February.
Pilot configuration in platform	Period where the configuration of the pilot sites in the INVADE platform is performed.	18/2/19	7/3/19	Platform integration and API test	When the integration is done, the configuration of the pilot sites in the INVADE platform can be performed.
Receive and visualize data	Period where the platform only receives and visualizes data.	11/3/19	Will last until pilot phase end	Pilot configuration in platform must be done	When the sites are configured, the platform is ready to start receiving relevant data from the pilot site. A period of historic data is necessary to have reliable predictions. A period of two months of historic data is seen as necessary.
Make predictions	Period to set up and schedule the	13/5/19	Will last until pilot	Receive and visualize	The first-time predictions are made, it takes some time to set them up and

	necessary predictions.		phase end		configure them. We must receive data for up to two months to make reliable predictions.
Run optimization	Period where flexibility is optimized at pilot sites, but devices not controlled.	27/5/19	Will last until pilot phase end	Make predictions	As soon as the predictions are set up to run, the optimization of flexibility can start up.
Send out control signals	Period to optimize flexibility and control devices.	15/06/19	Will last until pilot phase end	Run optimization	It is suggested to have a period with optimization running before actual control is performed. It is, in general, suggested that we don't start to control devices during the summer holiday period. This is July and Norway and possibly August in Germany? We then need to see if we can start the control after your holiday is done. Let's get back to this.

8.2 Pilot KPIs tests

Following the structure of Section 4, this chapter includes the test for the KPIs in all the pilot sites. Focus lays on description of the purpose, assumptions, pre-conditions, and test steps off all the KPIs.

8.2.1 Badenova

8.2.1.1 Test 1: DSO cost savings

This is not really a test but a calculator comparison of different solutions for the same problem in the same weak grid area. The challenge is to avoid over voltages there due to a high share of renewable energy generation. One solution could be strengthening the grid. This would trigger investments in energy lines with a higher capacity. Another one could be the use of battery storage. This calculation will be made for the real test case, where the CES is incorporated.

8.2.1.2 Test 2: Additional DSO cost savings

8.2.1.2.1 Purpose

The aim is cost savings regarding the peak power fees for the entire grid of bnNETZE to the upstream network operator.

8.2.1.2.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

The electrical grid of Badenova is not one meshed grid but three grids, which are not connected directly. For each part power fees to the higher voltage level grid operator have to be paid. The CES is located in the main grid, several DES also. Combined a maximum power of about 25 kW can be provided. This is not much compared to the peak load of about 120 MW, but the effect can be calculated as well as measured in real tests nevertheless.

8.2.1.2.3 Test steps

A calculation is to be made, which could be the maximum cost savings, if the maximum power of all storage units is available.

To make proof of concept test routines with example schedules are to be run. In these schedules the case is simulated, that without any special preliminary charging or discharging of the batteries the grid operator sends a peak shaving request in the morning and evening. Depending on the actual SOC of the batteries, the local PV generation and the electrical load in the affected households maybe not the full requested power is available. With these tests knowledge is to be built up, what can be expected in reality when maximum power is needed.

8.2.1.3 Test 3: Additional revenues for private households

8.2.1.3.1 Purpose

Amount of additional revenues for customers compared with common approach of optimizing self-sufficiency only.

8.2.1.3.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

The additional revenues depend strongly from a regulatory issue. In German legislation, grid friendly loads can be rewarded via reduced grid usage fees over the whole year. Unfortunately, storage devices are not clearly mentioned in the relevant law. So today is a questionable, if private customers opening their devices for external control can get

such a benefit. Badenova undertakes strong efforts to clear these issues with the German regulation authority. If we succeed, the joining customers can create a benefit between 25 and around 100 EUR on their residual electricity demand per year only due to decreased grid usage fees. On the other hand, Badenova can lower internal costs by avoiding peaks in the entire grid of bnNETZE.

8.2.1.3.3 Test steps

Calculations have to be done for different grid areas (not only bnNETZE), which benefit can be created for the customers. The benefit depends on the delta between regular grid usage fees and reduced grid usage fees. The delta is not always the same but depends on the local grid operator.

8.2.1.4 Test 4: Frequency of flexibility usage

8.2.1.4.1 Purpose

How frequently is flexibility requested by the DSO provided by DES and CES

8.2.1.4.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

This test is covered by Test 2.

8.2.1.4.3 Test steps

This test is covered by Test 2.

8.2.1.5 Test 5: Flexibility potential of DES

8.2.1.5.1 Purpose

Testing and examining the flexibility potential that DES can offer in addition to the actual purpose of optimizing self-consumption.

8.2.1.5.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

This test is covered by Test 2.

8.2.1.5.3 Test steps

This test is covered by Test 2.

8.3 Pilot Germany Deviations

The CES was delivered six week later than expected. But now it is in place and operational. All DES are operational. Deviations may only occur depending on the progress in other WPs affecting testing the communication link between INVADE platform and the test sites as well as later on full operation of the whole system.

9 Specifics for the pilot in Bulgaria

9.1 Objectives

9.1.1 Goals

The pilot in Albena, Bulgaria, demonstrates how a centralized battery storage and a number of controllable loads contribute to the overall energy efficiency of a group of consumers. It also addresses the benefits that electric vehicles can offer on its own and in combination with a centralized and stationary battery unit.

At the site of the five-star-hotel Flamingo Grand, a PV installation and a battery with inverter are installed to increase the share of the renewable energy that is used.

The motivation of the project is based on the fact that a large share of renewable energy sources brings volatility into the grid energy consumption. In some cases, this volatility could lead to financial penalties by the grid operators or energy suppliers, which would cause increase instead of decrease of the energy costs. By using battery storage systems and smart charging of EVs, the consumption of energy can be controlled/balanced. Energy management approaches like peak shaving, peak shifting, valley filling, etc., may change the form of the curve of used power. Using constant residual power from the grid will lead to financial benefits for the owner and thus, make the business model of the project profitable.

9.1.2 Main results

The implementation process of the pilot started with the installation and setup of the pilot infrastructure by the end of June 2018. The installation of the battery, the PV panels and the charging points have been done parallel. Adding them to the existing SCADA system has been done.

To the current moment, the effects of the added infrastructure is transparent and free to be observed at the SCADA system of Albena via a special dedicated web site www.albena.energy. A small demonstration of the energy management approaches will be done at the beginning of exploitation.

Ongoing is the connection of the SCADA system to the INVADE flexibility platform in order to send metering data and to receive control signals for the operation modes and also to send feedback information back. Based on that information the INVADE platform will be able to make decisions for the next step of optimization.

Real time market and weather data will be supplied to the IIP and on a next step this data will be also transferred to the Albena SCADA system. This small step is important for the later validation phase of the project, during which the results of the pilot will be made accessible to the public.

9.1.3 Final list of KPIs to be measured

Table 30. KPIs specifically for the Albena pilot

KPI no	Key Performance Indicator	Definition	PUC
1	Cost savings from optimized energy flows	Cost savings due to optimized time of use of energy on the day-ahead market	1 and 2
2	Cost savings from increased RES share	Cost savings due to decreased delivery energy because of local generation	2
3	% decreased max power	Decreased max delivery power due to optimized energy flows and adjusted Time of Use	1 and 2
4	Frequency of flexibility	Number of requests by the BRP for consumed power increase or decrease	1 and 2
5	Stick to a predefined load profile	Deviation from a predefined load profile	2

9.1.4 Implementation process

For the different types of “sub-pilots”/locations in the pilot, there will be a different time frame for the implementation process.

According to the deliverable D10.2 and the time frame defined all the tasks and subtasks state is explained and detailed below:

Table 30. Pilot implementation process

Time Frame	Sub-pilot	Details
2017.08 – 2018.05	Whole pilot	Regulatory analysis, Load profiles' analysis, Accounting and business case analysis, dimensioning and pilot design, analysis of controllable loads, SCADA design and implementation Control of loads system enhancement
2017.04 – 2017.08	Hotels Borjana and Paradise Blue, sub-pilot – Controllable Loads	On the boiler room of Hotel Borjana as a future controllable load work on the hydraulic connections have been performed. In the same time the boiler room of the newly built Hotel Paradise Blue has been done in the same manner as Hotel Borjana. Both boiler rooms are part of the later created "Albena Flexibility Cloud", part of the Invade Integrated Platform
2017.08 – 2018.03	Subtask controllable loads	Improvement of the system that controls the boiler stations. The work is expressed in further possibility that is available thanks to the successfully performed change of the hydraulic connections in the Boiler Room of Borjana
2018.05	Flamingo Grand Hotel	Contract with battery and PV deliverer

2018.06	Flamingo Grand Hotel	Battery and PV installation done
2018.04 – 2018.09	Subtask: Controllable loads	All controllable loads are integrated and are ready to perform flexibility tasks
2018.07 – 2018.09	Whole pilot	First battery and PV exploitation, staff training, SCADA further development. More than 180 metering points have been installed
2018.10 – 2018.11	Flamingo Grand Hotel	Manual battery exploitation according to the energy consumption of the loads First steps in controlling the battery via modbus. Parallel: further development of control of loads system
2018.09 – 2019.03	Communications of the pilot to the IIP	Integration between Albena SCADA and INVADE Integrated Platform Configuration of the pilot in the IIP First manual transmission of metering data to the IIP
2019.03 – 2019.04	Communications of the pilot to the IIP	Supply of metering data to the IIP automatically Receive of market and weather data into the SCADA Receive automatically and evaluate manually first control signals for optimized energy flows according to the day ahead market.

2019.05	Control Signals' Implementation	Start of implementation of control signals based solely on the day ahead market prices
2019.06	Control Signals' Implementation	Enhancement of the predictions by considering also weather data
2019.07 – 2019.10	Tests	Conduct tests and collect data for later evaluation of the KPIs
2019.10 – 2019.12	Tests and evaluation	Proceed with the tests for low-season optimizations. Prepare final report of the impact

9.2 Pilot KPIs tests

9.2.1 Albena

Following the structure of Section 4, include the test for the KPIs in each pilot. With the purpose, assumptions, pre-conditions, and steps off all the KPIs

9.2.1.1 Test 1: Cost savings from optimized energy flows

9.2.1.1.1 Purpose

To achieve real financial benefit from the adjusted power flows Albena will try to shift energy demand from high-priced-hours on the day-ahead-market to lower-priced hours.

9.2.1.1.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

In order to make a good prediction and validate it, necessary data is:

- Metering data
- Market data

9.2.1.1.3 Test steps

First and most important step is to have market data available. The hour prices for the next coming day are vital for financial benefit as impact created by INVADE.

Based on them, the power consumption for the next day should be rescheduled so that most of it is consumed in moments at low energy prices.

After the end of the day evaluation needs to be done.

The cost for the energy of the day is compared to the cost that Albena would pay for a normal day load profile without adjustment.

	Action	Expected result	Result
1.	Receive Market Data available	Hour prices	
2.	Reschedule power consumption for next day	New schedules for energy at low energy prices	
3.	After the day new evaluation required		
4.	Compare cost of energy to Albena cost for normal day	New prices	

9.2.1.2 Test 2: Cost savings from increased RES share

9.2.1.2.1 Purpose

The power flows adjustment needs to consider the RES generation. In some cases when the energy is very cheap, an algorithm that doesn't consider the RES could send control signal that loads the boilers with hot water. Later, when also the sun generates hot water in the solar thermal stations, could possibly lead to over-heating and further infrastructure problems.

9.2.1.2.2 Assumptions and pre-conditions

- Metering data
- Market data
- Weather data

9.2.1.2.3 Test steps

The algorithms in the IIP need to predict not only the consumption, but also the RES generation. The evaluation will take into account the RES potential of the day and compare it to the actually utilized potential.

9.2.1.3 Test 3: % decreased max power

The optimized energy flows include the kWmax optimization which means that they will avoid power congestions.

9.2.1.3.1 Assumptions and pre-conditions

- Metering data
- Market data
- Weather data

9.2.1.3.2 Test steps

After the day the peak power values will be compared to the peak power values of a normal day without optimization.

9.2.1.4 Test 4: Frequency of flexibility

This is not a test, but rather a measure of the potential for providing services to third parties by offering flexibility. Larger the number of flexibility requests will show that the BRP thrusters the technology and workflows. The requests can be done manually, no integration with their systems will be done in order to remain as general as possible.

9.2.1.5 Stick to a predefined load profile

Important KPI for tariffs that are based on standard load profiles. The ability to stick to a certain one defines the tariff that the energy consumer will get from the supplier.

9.2.1.5.1 Assumptions and pre-conditions

- Metering data
- Predefined load profile
- Market data
- Weather data

9.2.1.5.2 Test steps

After the day the deviations from the predefined load profile will be evaluated and imbalance prices will be applied.

9.3 Pilot Albena deviations

There are no deviations currently detected. Moreover, the test design agenda represents even shorter periods of implementation and evaluation in order to ensure longer period of tests.